

Engaging across the “Iron Curtain”: Transnational Student Exchanges between Czechoslovakia and the United Kingdom, 1948–1970⁸³

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Abstract

This article examines transnational elements of university student exchanges across the “Iron Curtain,” more precisely between the United Kingdom and the Czechoslovak Socialist Republic. Drawing on a range of contemporary newspapers, like the mainstream The Guardian and The New York Times, alongside governmental documents from British and Czech archives as well as Czechoslovak student magazines such as Impuls and Student, the article examines the interaction opportunities between Czechoslovak and British students that were enabled through The British-Czechoslovak Cultural Exchange between 1948 and the 1970s. This article proves that student networks did not appear unexpectedly in the 1960s. It argues that Czechoslovak students were part of a wider, transnationally dynamic student network before 1968, thus challenging the notion of the impenetrability of the “Iron Curtain.” Moreover, the article not only considers the political events of the Prague Spring, but also draws attention to students who studied or found exile in Britain during the years both before and after 1968. In doing so, it highlights the response of the British student body to the Warsaw Pact invasion of Czechoslovakia in August 1968, which resulted in the launch of the Czechoslovak Students’ Scholarship Fund.

Keywords: Student Networks – Transnational History – Czechoslovak-British Relations – The 1960s – Czechoslovak Students' Scholarship Fund

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Introduction

The term “Iron Curtain” tempts us to believe that any movement across the borders of Western and Soviet blocs was impossible. However, historical research, especially on student activism, has been proposing otherwise for at least two decades.⁸⁴ For instance, Gildea, Mark and Warring point out that “the true 1968 was seen essentially as a Western phenomenon,” and they aim to transcend this notion by highlighting “the penetrability of the Iron Curtain in this period.”⁸⁵ This article aims to contribute to this literature by focusing on exchanges of university students between the Czechoslovak Socialist Republic and the United Kingdom. It suggests that the research on “student activism” can be vital for better understanding the present and future student unrest, as Caroline Hoefflerle maintains.⁸⁶ Centring the research around transnational student movements, such as that from Czechoslovakia, can equally contribute to this historical debate. By revealing possibilities for interactions across the borders of the Cold War, this paper further demonstrates that the notion of an impenetrable “Iron Curtain” is flawed and outdated.

The historiographical debate concerning worldwide student activism of 1968 had already begun in the 1970s not only by acknowledging the role of mass media and international meetings in accelerating the spread of student activism, but also by denying the existence of “real international student ‘movement’” as such.⁸⁷ Concerning protests that emerged in great numbers throughout the world and their connection to the rise of Détente, Jeremi Suri argues that the focus on the 1960s “reveals how ideas, institutions, and personalities transcended national boundaries.”⁸⁸ Suri’s argument thus gives this project the necessary impulse. It is due to boundary-outreaching institutions and individuals, that it is possible to learn about the British-Czechoslovak state-issued scholarship exchanges and students stranded in the United Kingdom after August 1968.

The historiography of the British student body and its activism in the 1960s argues “that the British student movement both responded and contributed to [...] international dissent movements in the era of the Long Sixties.”⁸⁹ Therefore, this article seeks to support this argument

⁸⁴ See for example Robert Gildea, James Mark, and Anette Warring, eds., *Europe’s 1968: Voices of Revolt* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2013); Ronald Fraser, ed., *1968: A Student Generation in Revolt* (New York: Pantheon Books, 1988); Gerd-Rainer Horn and Padraic Kenney eds., *Transnational Moments of Change: Europe 1945, 1968, 1989* (Lanham: Rowman & Littlefield, 2004); Richard I. Jobs and David M. Pomfret, *Transnational Histories of Youth in the Twentieth Century* (Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan, 2015); Richard Ivan Jobs, *Backpack Ambassadors: How Youth Travel Integrated Europe* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2017).

⁸⁵ Gildea, Mark, and Warring, eds., *Europe’s 1968*, 3, 328.

⁸⁶ Caroline Hoefflerle, *British Student Activism in the Long Sixties* (New York: Routledge, 2013), 2.

⁸⁷ Philip G. Altbach, “The International Student Movement,” *Journal of Contemporary History* 5, no. 1 (1970): 169, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/259987>.

⁸⁸ Jeremi Suri, *Power and Protest: Global Revolution and the Rise of Detente* (Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 2005), 262.

⁸⁹ Hoefflerle, *British Student Activism in the Long Sixties*, 2.

by analysing responses of British students to the Czechoslovak experience of 1968.⁹⁰ It aims to do so by introducing the case of the Czechoslovak Students' Scholarship Fund.

As already proposed, this contribution takes a transnational approach to the histories of Czechoslovak students, and especially takes into account Pierre-Yves Saunier's approach to transnational history that "acknowledges and assesses foreign contributions to (...) domestic communities, politics and societies, and vice versa," and Gerd-Rainer Horn and Padraic Kenney's understanding of transnationalism "as the study of similarities, parallels, or connectors across national frontiers."⁹¹ It is, therefore, clear that the following discussion is not a comparative study, but rather an analysis of the Czechoslovak student movement's transnational dynamics with the United Kingdom and its student bodies.

Ludovic Tournès and Giles Scott-Smith's edited volume provides a great source for researching student exchanges, which, according to Tournès and Smith, "[have] not received the historical attention [they] deserve."⁹² Additionally, Rachel Applebaum's work captures the student exchanges between Czechoslovakia and the Soviet Union.⁹³ Consequently, this article aims to, at least partially, fill in the research gap of student exchanges between Czechoslovakia and the West. Therefore, drawing on the above-mentioned secondary literature, this article aims to contribute to the field of transnational history and position the history of the Czechoslovak student movement on the transnational scene.

The Cold War period witnessed a rapid increase in international student organisations, such as the World Federation of Democratic Youth (WFDY), set up in London in 1945, the International Union of Students (IUS), of which Czechoslovak student unions were part, and its rival organisation International Student Conference (ISC). The Soviet Union controlled both the WFDY and the IUS, which was founded in Prague in 1946, whereas, the CIA sponsored the ISC, which was founded in 1950 in Stockholm by twenty-one national unions that broke away from the IUS.⁹⁴ All of these organisations influenced transnational connections between Czechoslovak and

⁹⁰ For further reading on other transnational connections of Czechoslovak students, see Simon Hall, *1956: The World in Revolt* (London: Faber & Faber, 2016); Tom Junes, *Student Politics in Communist Poland: Generations of Consent and Dissent* (Lanham: Lexington Books, 2015).

⁹¹ Pierre-Yves Saunier, *Transnational History* (Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan, 2013), 3; Kenney and Horn, "Introduction: Approaches to the Transnational," in *Transnational Moments of Change*, xi.

⁹² Ludovic Tournès and Giles Scott-Smith, "Introduction: A World of Exchanges," in *Global Exchanges: Scholarships and Transnational Circulations in the Modern World*, eds. Ludovic Tournès and Giles Scott-Smith (New York: Berghahn Books, 2017), 2.

⁹³ Rachel Applebaum, *Empire of Friends: Soviet Power and Socialist Internationalism in Cold War Czechoslovakia* (Ithaca: Cornell University Press, 2019).

⁹⁴ Joël Kotek, *Students and the Cold War* (New York: St. Martin's Press, 1996), xii.

British students, for instance through the *First World Youth Festival* in 1947, or conferences, where students debated about politics and discussed their universal experiences.⁹⁵

Drawing on a range of contemporary newspapers and government documents from British and Czech archives as well as student magazines, this article examines transnational elements of student activism in the Czechoslovak Socialist Republic during the events preceding the social and political upheavals of the Prague Spring and the following crisis of August 1968. The first part covers student engagement through the programme of The British-Czechoslovak Cultural Exchange between 1948 and the 1960s, in order to argue that student networks did not appear unexpectedly in the 1960s as well as to demonstrate the opportunities for student interaction on an international level and for development of transnational networks. It suggests that the “Iron Curtain” was not as impenetrable as it might have seemed. The second part examines student transnational structures and their impact during the 1960s and the notorious Prague Spring with an emphasis on the role of the British student body in aiding Czechoslovak students in Britain through the *Czechoslovak Students’ Scholarship Fund* (CSSF). In doing so, the article illustrates the international solidarity among students and how transnational networks became beneficial at the time of crisis. It is, thus, clear that the article’s scope is marked by crucial events in Czechoslovak history in the twentieth century. These are the communist takeover in 1948, after which the Czechoslovak Republic essentially became a satellite of the Soviet bloc, and the Warsaw Pact invasion in 1968. Both events are thoroughly discussed below since this project also points out the Cold War’s influence on Czechoslovak student activism. Nevertheless, due to the availability of primary sources, this article follows only university students, mostly from Prague universities.

Czechoslovakia and the Student Exchanges after the Second World War

“Prague is now known to be one of the chief centres for indoctrinating youth (...)” states a letter from the British Foreign Office to the British Council in September 1949.⁹⁶ This notion formed an attitude towards the British Council scholarships for Czechoslovak students only a year and a half after the communist takeover of power in Czechoslovakia. However, this was not always the case. In 1943, “an exchange of students between the United States and Slavic countries was in existence prior to this [second world] war and had an important cultural and political function.”⁹⁷

⁹⁵95 Altbach, “The International Student Movement,” 169.

⁹⁶ The National Archives, Kew (hereafter: TNA), BW 27/16, British Council Scholarships for Czech students: policy, “Extract from a letter from J. P. G. Finch Esq., Foreign Office to R. Seymour Esq., C. B. E., The British Council,” September 8, 1949.

⁹⁷ Josef Brožek, “European Slavs and Student Exchange with the United States,” *Bulletin of the American Association of University Professors* (1915–1955) 29, no. 3 (1943): 387, accessed July 4, 2023, doi:10.2307/40220450. Additionally, for personal testimony about studying in the United Kingdom during the 1920s see Sylva Šimsová, *Zasviť mi, ty slunko zlaté:*

The same can be observed in the United Kingdom as well. A scheme from 1935 to 1936 by the British Council allocated bursaries for students from eleven countries, including Czechoslovakia, who “had expressed a desire for ‘furthering the study of English.’”⁹⁸ Additionally, it was proposed that Czechoslovakia was deserving of “special attention” in distributing the bursaries due to the influence of the first Czechoslovak president, Tomáš Garrigue Masaryk.⁹⁹ Clearly, there has been a tradition to follow after the end of the Second World War. This student exchange “trend” was renewed in 1945–1946 as the British Council assigned nine scholarships (out of one hundred) to Czechoslovakia.¹⁰⁰ Apart from official student exchanges, there were other opportunities for interaction between the students of Czechoslovakia and Britain. They illustrate the connectedness of young adults in the period before the 1960s. Students had opportunities to meet their peers, for example, at the *First World Festival of Youth and Students*, which was organised by WFDY and IUS in Prague, just a year before the communist coup, in 1947. More than twenty thousand young people from abroad attended the festival, which enabled them to establish some international student contacts.¹⁰¹

Nonetheless, as already apparent such exchanges were to be terminated. In 1946, the Czech Communist Party (Komunistická strana Československa, KSČ) won the first national elections after the Second World War, and its leader, Klement Gottwald became the prime minister. This victory of the Communist Party paved the way for a gradual takeover of political power in the country.¹⁰² Although the KSČ initially assembled a government with democratic parties, communist politicians increased pressure on the democratic ones which resulted in the demission of twelve democratic ministers on 20 February 1948.¹⁰³ These politicians counted on the support of other ministers from the government as they needed to have at least thirteen resignations to declare new elections. However, no other ministers resigned, therefore, communists took advantage of the political situation when Gottwald went to negotiate with the president, Edvard

Ze vzpomínek Jarky Maiwaldové a Sylvy Šimsově na Domov (Prague: Municipal Library in Prague, 2022), 98–102. Young Czechoslovaks were able to study abroad due to scholarships, such as the Rockefeller scholarship, as the case of Karel Maiwald demonstrates.

⁹⁸ Alice Byrne, “A ‘Sound Investment’? British Cultural Diplomacy and Overseas Students: The British Council’s Students Committee, 1935–1939,” *Contemporary European History* 30, no. 2 (2021): 271, doi:10.1017/S0960777321000072.

⁹⁹ Byrne, “A ‘Sound Investment’?,” 271.

¹⁰⁰ Zora Damová, “Československé školství ve Velké Británii (1940–1945),” (MA thesis, Charles University, 2013), <https://dspace.cuni.cz/handle/20.500.11956/52690>, 116. See also Jan Kuklík and Jan Němeček, *Osvobozené Československo očima britské diplomacie: zprávy britské ambasády z Prahy v roce 1945*, ed. Marie Bernardová, (Prague: Karolinum, 2010), 319–320.

¹⁰¹ Kotek, *Students and the Cold War*, 117.

¹⁰² Laura Cashman, “Remembering 1948 and 1968: Reflections on Two Pivotal Years in Czech and Slovak History,” *Europe-Asia Studies* 60, no. 10 (2008): 1646, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/20451652>.

¹⁰³ Václav Veber, “Jak to bylo s demisemi v únoru 1948,” *Paměť a Dějiny* 1 (2009): 6, <https://www.ustrcr.cz/data/pdf/pamet-dejiny/pad0901/005-010.pdf>.

Beneš, about forming a new, fully communist government. Gottwald succeeded on 25 February and became president on 14 June 1948, thus cementing the communist influence in the country.¹⁰⁴

The seeming unity of the international youth, apparent at the *First World Festival*, did not have a long duration and was put under pressure when the state police attacked Czechoslovak students during their protests in February 1948. The beating also influenced the British National Union of Students of England, Scotland and Wales (NUS) which discussed its possible withdrawal from the IUS at a Council meeting held at Oxford in July 1948, attended also by Czechoslovak students to testify about the situation in their home country.¹⁰⁵ This demonstrates the transnational dynamics of the Czechoslovak student movement as well as student structures since Czechoslovak delegates had a chance to attend a meeting of another country's national student union. Nevertheless, testimonies of Czechoslovak students did not make much difference in the NUS since it decided not to withdraw from the IUS yet. The decision to leave the organisation came only in February 1951 after yet another series of troubles within the IUS, among which was the increasing involvement of the Soviet Union in the IUS, and the issue of the Korean War.¹⁰⁶

Naturally, the transformation of the Czechoslovak political scene had an impact on its domestic and international policy. The altered travel policy and visa issuance also affected young people, especially students who wished to study abroad. After the coup, the new state government aimed to restrain the movement of citizens to foreign countries, so it produced a new set of policies dealing with trips abroad, visa issuance, and the arrival of foreigners in 1949.¹⁰⁷ The KSČ intended to minimise travel in both directions to "the smallest possible measure."¹⁰⁸ Some international connections were disrupted as the state began deciding who would be let to travel abroad. This was also the case of the British Council scholarships issued for Czechoslovaks and vice versa. Another letter from the Foreign Office to the British Council offers a useful insight into troubles that were caused by the shift of Czechoslovakia into the Soviet zone of influence, such as the fear of Czechoslovak authorities indoctrinating British students: "The harm done by letting Britons be indoctrinated in Czechoslovakia is greater than the harm Czech indoctrinators can do to our people during visits here."¹⁰⁹ This document also demonstrates that student and academic exchanges

¹⁰⁴ Cashman, "Remembering 1948 and 1968," 1647.

¹⁰⁵ Kotek, *Students and the Cold War*, 137. As mentioned below, policies restricting travel abroad, visas, and foreign visits were introduced only in 1949, thus enabling travel abroad in 1948. See footnote 106.

¹⁰⁶ Kotek, *Students and the Cold War*, 181.

¹⁰⁷ The party wanted to minimize the emigration of valuable citizens abroad. Jan Rychlík, *Cestování do ciziny v habsburské monarchii a v Československu: pasová, vízová a vystěhovalcká politika, 1848-1989* (Prague: Ústav pro soudobé dějiny AV ČR, 2007), 35.

¹⁰⁸ Rychlík, *Cestování do ciziny v habsburské monarchii a v Československu*, 36.

¹⁰⁹ TNA, BW 27/16, "British Council Scholarships for Czech students: policy," J. P. G. Finch, Esq. to R. Seymour, Esq., September 13, 1949.

became the centre of a dispute between the two countries after the February coup, additionally because of the problem with student selection – the countries were unable to agree if either the country providing the students, or the one receiving them, should select the student for exchanges.¹¹⁰ This was again a result of suspicion on both sides. Therefore, the communist government's reluctance to allow people to leave the country on one hand, and the British officials' fear of indoctrination of British students on the other, simultaneously affected state-issued exchanges.

Therefore, the Cold War climate clearly influenced the lives of students since they also suffered the consequences of cooling political relations. Tournès and Scott-Smith argue that scholarships during the Cold War were “ultra-politicized.”¹¹¹ It is evident that the same can be proposed about state-issued scholarships between Czechoslovakia and the United Kingdom. Eventually, due to the hesitance of the Czechoslovak government to grant passports to students who were chosen for the exchange by the British Council, and non-compliance with the agreement made between the two countries, the cultural relationships had been treated as “dead for the time being” since 1 May 1950.¹¹² Interestingly, the inability of governments to agree on new terms of cultural and academic exchange in the then-contemporary political situation disrupted possible transnational relations that students could have built. Furthermore, in 1952, changes to the visa policy produced a burst of bureaucracy requiring citizens to fill in numerous forms with reasonable explanations for their travels.¹¹³ Consequently, the difficulty surrounding travelling abroad became one of the complaints of the Czechoslovak student movement in 1956.

Change in Visa Policy and Travel: Renewal of Exchanges

The atmosphere of the 1950s was filled with fear as KSČ organised judicial show trials.¹¹⁴ The second half of the 1950s saw a slight relaxation after the death of the General Secretary of the Communist Party, Joseph Stalin in 1953. In the same year, President Gottwald's death as well as the Twentieth Congress of the Communist Party of the USSR in 1956 further affected the situation in Czechoslovakia. Despite the succession of anti-reform presidents, Antonín Zápotocký in 1953 and Antonín Novotný in 1957, Czechoslovak students became active in the production of so-

¹¹⁰ TNA, BW 27/16, “Anglo-Czechoslovak Cultural Relations: Scholarships,” R. A. Close, October 11, 1949.

¹¹¹ Tournès and Scott-Smith, “Introduction,” in *Global Exchanges*, eds. Tournès and Scott-Smith, 15.

¹¹² TNA, BW 27/16, “British Council Scholarships for Czech students: policy,” Confidential letter on British Council Scholarships from T. H. Sears to the Representative of the British Council in Prague, 1 May 1950. However, exchanges with the Soviet Union continued, see Rachel Applebaum, “The Land of Our Destiny,” in *Empire of Friends*, 50–80.

¹¹³ Rychlík, *Cestování do ciziny v habsburské monarchii a v Československu*, 40.

¹¹⁴ Pavlína Formánková, “Vypořádali jsme se s Horákovou, vypořádáme se i s americkým broukem!,” *Paměť a dějiny* 1 (2007): 20–41, <https://www.ustrcr.cz/data/pdf/pamet-dejiny/0701-20-41.pdf>.

called resolutions in the early spring of 1956.¹¹⁵ Students of the Faculty of Mathematics and Physics at Charles University in Prague were among the first to produce a resolution. The text not only called for improvements in the “system of electing candidates to the National Committee and National Assembly,” thus pointing out political reforms, but they also asked for the transformation of student life:

“We ask that travel to foreign countries be made possible other than through the Czechoslovak State Travel Agency. We urge special emphasis on exchange agreements, particularly those involving students, with minimalisation of foreign currency difficulties ... We also consider it necessary that procedures for obtaining permission to travel abroad (which at present require filling out fourteen forms) be significantly simplified.”¹¹⁶

This indicates that students were well aware of difficulties relating to studying abroad and wanted to gain new experiences and establish new connections in foreign countries. Consequently, the government considered the content of this and similar resolutions as “anti-state” and resisted the distribution of the texts through secret uncovering of the individuals who distributed resolutions resulting in “criminal liability and prophylactic measures.”¹¹⁷

It took three more years until the next communist government allowed changes to visa and travel policy. As Jan Rychlík points out, the initial alterations from 1956 were concerned with travel to “the Soviet Union and people’s democracies (...) and visits to the West were organised rather exceptionally.”¹¹⁸ He nonetheless confirms these tours were indeed taking place, although to a lesser extent than trips to the East. Moreover, the KSC was especially concerned with sending the “right,” meaning verified, people to capitalist countries.¹¹⁹ This demonstrates that the Foreign Office’s anxieties about the indoctrination, discussed above, ahead of suspending the Programme of Cultural Exchanges with Czechoslovakia, were justified.

With a transformation of visa and travel policy, Czechoslovakia opened to travellers from all around the world. According to a report from 1958, there was an increase of “14.200 applications for travel documents” compared to 1957.¹²⁰ Although the mobility of young

¹¹⁵ Interestingly, in 1956, students also played a vital role in “drawing up a list of demands (...) which would become the manifesto of the Hungarian revolution”; See Hall, *1956: The World in Revolt*, 295. Additionally, Tom Junes argued that “the parallels between Polish, Czech, Slovak, and Hungarian student activism in 1956 suggest they bore some transnational generational characteristics”; see Junes, *Student Politics in Communist Poland* (Lanham: Lexington Books, 2015), 53–4.

¹¹⁶ “Resolution adopted by the School Organization of the Czechoslovak Youth Union, School of Mathematics and Physics,” Charles University, Prague, April 26, 1956, trans. by Professor Charles E. Townsend, Princeton University reproduced in *Majáles 1956: The Abortive Student Revolt in Czechoslovakia in 1956*, ed. John P. C. Matthews, (Brno: Prius, 2000), 39–45.

¹¹⁷ Archiv bezpečnostních složek, Prague (hereafter: ABS), A 6/3 i.j. 993, “Tajný rozkaz MV č. 51/1956: Rozpracování nepřátelských elementů z řad studentů – zajištění,” June 1956.

¹¹⁸ Rychlík, *Cestování do ciziny v habsburské monarchii a v Československu*, 55–57.

¹¹⁹ Rychlík, *Cestování do ciziny v habsburské monarchii a v Československu*, 57.

¹²⁰ Rychlík, *Cestování do ciziny v habsburské monarchii a v Československu*, 59.

people was a distinct feature of 1968, there is evidence of student travel from previous years as well. For example, representatives of Czechoslovakia attended the Tenth International Student Travel Conference in Edinburgh held in 1959.¹²¹ Additionally, Richard Ivan Jobs suggests that this “transnational mobility” aided in “invigorat[ing] local movements.”¹²²

Moreover, the above-mentioned exchange programmes for university students played an important role as well. These were mostly conducted through University Interchange Schemes, which were, in the case of the United Kingdom, a part of the Programme of Cultural Exchanges between Czechoslovakia and the United Kingdom. As is apparent from the previous section of this article, this programme was temporarily terminated in 1950. However, Czechoslovakia initiated talks about renewing this scheme in 1958, firstly in terms of university scholars.¹²³ The committee for the University Interchange Scheme saw such interaction as beneficial for establishing contacts between universities.¹²⁴ The Czechoslovak students, on the other hand, based their claims for less strict travel to the Western universities on reservations about “mechanically adopting the Soviet experience,” suggesting they wanted to gain experience also from other countries.¹²⁵ It could be therefore argued that the easing of the Cold War climate on both sides of the “Iron Curtain” and the developing political situation in Czechoslovakia influenced the change of travel policy, which greatly impacted opportunities for international student travel and consequently interactions.

Student exchanges: Scholarships and Summer Camps

The proposal for exchange between Czechoslovak and British universities was first discussed in terms of academic interchange and the Universities Advisory Committee of the British Council welcomed it.¹²⁶ However, it is not precisely clear when this scheme reopened as the correspondence between the British Embassy in Prague, which hosted members of the Czechoslovak Ministry of Education and Culture, and the British Foreign Office, spans until 1960. Nonetheless, it is safe to assume that an agreement was reached during the early 1960s since a letter from the Foreign Office, dated 15 January 1964, mentions arrangements for the same programme

¹²¹ “Student Travel: Conference Opens to Communists,” *The Guardian*, October 28, 1959, 3, <https://www.proquest.com/hnpguardianobserver/docview/184600490/citation/65CE396BF4704D1FPO/12>.

¹²² Richard Ivan Jobs, “Youth Movements: Travel, Protest, and Europe in 1968,” *The American Historical Review* 114, no. 2 (2009): 384, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/30223784>.

¹²³ TNA, BW 27/22, “University Interchange Scheme (1958–1968),” P. H. Moberly to Mr White, August 5, 1958.

¹²⁴ TNA, BW 27/22, “University Interchange Scheme (1958–1968),” Letter from S. W. White (Director, Universities and Adult Education Department) to Mr Moberly (British Embassy, Prague), October 31, 1958.

¹²⁵ “Resolution adopted by the School Organization of the Czechoslovak Youth Union, School of Mathematics and Physics,” Charles University, Prague, April 26, 1956, trans. by Professor Charles E. Townsend, Princeton University reproduced in *Majáles 1956*, ed. John P. C. Matthews, 39–45.

¹²⁶ TNA, BW 27/22, “University Interchange Scheme (1958–1968),” a letter from H. Harvey Wood, October 28, 1958.

from 1963/64.¹²⁷ Therefore, these materials indicate that “the impossibility of travelling to Western universities,” which for example Kristina Andělová identifies as one of the frequent complaints in numerous Czechoslovak student magazines, was not as great as emphasised in academic literature.¹²⁸ Moreover, the notion of the impassable “Iron Curtain” must be challenged here, as James Mark and Robert Gildea have done previously, when they argued that the “Iron Curtain” was permeable.¹²⁹

From 1963/64, exchanges operated on an annual basis as each year talks between representatives of Czechoslovakia discussed the issue with the United Kingdom. Section IV of an aide-mémoire produced on 26 February 1964 mentions that: “(...) both sides agree to facilitate exchanges of visits between groups of students and young people in which the visitors will be given opportunities to meet students and young people in the receiving country and to acquaint themselves with their work, studies, and social life.”¹³⁰ This section was added on the initiative of British representatives, despite their awareness of the Czechoslovak Youth Union (*Československý svaz mládeže*, ČSM) being under the direct influence of the KSČ.¹³¹ This demonstrates that although the suspicions resulting from the Cold War climate persisted, they no longer influenced the young people and students’ lives as the two parties continued a discussion about “the exact position of the CSM vis á vis the NUS.”¹³² It is significant that the governments of both countries consciously intended for students to interact since they must have known that this would lead to an exchange of ideas, such as that about political development, between the young people. Overall, it is apparent that the British side intended for student interaction in hopes of influencing them.

Furthermore, apart from student exchanges during the regular academic year, young people had also a chance to encounter their counterparts from across the “Iron Curtain” during summer camps. While it was argued that “Western communist youth engaged with their Eastern bloc comrades at summer camps on the other side of the Iron Curtain,” this interaction also functioned the other way around.¹³³ This can be observed from a correspondence relating to the Anglo-Czechoslovak Cultural Agreement from 1966–68, which states that nine places at summer

¹²⁷ TNA, BW 27/28, “UK-Czechoslovakia Programme of Cultural Exchanges 1964–1965,” R. L. Speaight to C. C. Parrot, January 15, 1964.

¹²⁸ Kristina Andělová, “Czechoslovak Generational Experience of 1968: The Intellectual History Perspective,” *East European Politics and Societies* 33, no. 4 (2019): 892, [doi:10.1177/0888325419864418](https://doi.org/10.1177/0888325419864418).

¹²⁹ James Mark and Robert Gildea, “Conclusion: Europe’s 1968,” in *Europe’s 1968: Voices of Revolt* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2013), eds. Robert Gildea, James Mark, Anette Warring, 328.

¹³⁰ TNA, “BW 27/28, UK-Czechoslovakia Programme of Cultural Exchanges 1964–1965,” Aide-mémoire, Section IV, February 26, 1964.

¹³¹ TNA, “BW 27/28, UK-Czechoslovakia Programme of Cultural Exchanges 1964–1965,” a letter from R. L. Speaight to C. C. Parrot, February 27, 1964.

¹³² TNA, “BW 27/28, UK-Czechoslovakia Programme of Cultural Exchanges 1964–1965,” Minutes of Talks, February 25–26, 1964.

¹³³ James Mark and Robert Gildea, “Conclusion: Europe’s 1968,” in *Europe’s 1968*, eds. Gildea, Mark, and Warring, 328.

camps were allocated to students from Czechoslovakia.¹³⁴ To give one example of the already mentioned summer camps, between 7 and 28 August 1966, ten students were received at the National Union of Students' Summer School Loughborough.¹³⁵

The British Council and the Ministry of Education and Culture agreed to operate a programme of cultural exchange similar to the ones from previous years between 1 April 1966 and 31 March 1968.¹³⁶ These university exchanges were promoted in student journals, such as *Impuls* (published by students from the University of Agriculture in Prague), which states that for 1968, "exchanges are planned with the University of Leeds and Scottish Agricultural College in Auchincruive."¹³⁷ Additionally, between the years 1966 and 1967, 80 young people participated in the student and youth exchanges with the "level of exchanges (...) slightly increased in comparison with the last year."¹³⁸ British institutions included in the programme at this time were, for example, the University of Leeds, the University of Strathclyde, Glasgow Veterinary College, Reading University and Birmingham University.

Therefore, students, and young people in general, had opportunities for interaction in the years preceding 1968. On these occasions, Czechoslovak and British students had opportunities to establish structures that became valuable after the August crisis in 1968, as is discussed below. These interactions mentioned so far, can be described in the words of Akira Irie and Pierre-Yves Saunier as "transnational processes of exchange" creating a distinct culture of the "Sixties" which translated itself into "social and cultural transformations."¹³⁹

It is thus evident that a discussion about the transformation of domestic policy in Czechoslovakia, namely the communist seizure of power in February 1948, is necessary to understand the conditions under which the Czechoslovak students were living. The global cooling of political relations between the Eastern and West blocs affected Czechoslovak students through the shift of Czechoslovakia behind the "Iron Curtain" which led to travel restrictions. Transnational structures of the Czechoslovak student movement, which might have found its roots already before the Second World War, or during the *First World Festival of Youth and Students*

¹³⁴ TNA, BW 27/30, "UK-Czechoslovakia Programme of Cultural Exchanges 1966-1968," a letter from S. W. White, October 14, 1965.

¹³⁵ TNA, BW 27/30, "UK-Czechoslovakia Programme of Cultural Exchanges 1966-1968," Anglo-Czechoslovak Programme of Cultural Exchanges 1965/66: Mid-year Report on the Progress of the Implementation of Exchanges, 12, September 30, 1965.

¹³⁶ TNA, BW 27/30, "UK-Czechoslovakia Programme of Cultural Exchanges 1966-1968," a letter from S. G. West, March 29, 1966.

¹³⁷ "Zahraniční výbor," *Impuls* 4, no. 1 (November 1967): 24, accessed October 7, 2021, <https://www.libpro.cz/studentske-casopisy/>.

¹³⁸ TNA, BW 27/30, "UK-Czechoslovakia Programme of Cultural Exchanges 1966-1968," Report on the Progress of the Implementation of Exchanges 1966/67, 13-14, June 1966.

¹³⁹ Akira Irie and Pierre-Yves Saunier, *The Palgrave Dictionary of Transnational History* (Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan, 2009), 2.

in 1947, were disrupted. British-Czechoslovak student relations were utilised, for example, at the already mentioned NUS Conference in 1948, which some democratic Czechoslovak delegates attended.

Nevertheless, a major development of transnational connections between the student bodies of the two countries occurred during a period of relaxation of communist policy within Czechoslovakia in the late 1950s and early 1960s. The transforming policy of Czechoslovakia regarding travel and visas played a significant role in opportunities for students to interact with their peers from the United Kingdom. This transformation was accompanied by students' calls for the easing of travel restrictions, which is apparent from the 1956 student resolutions. As the Foreign Office documentation and British Council correspondence have demonstrated, there were several occasions during which students from both countries could have established useful networks. The summer camps and student exchanges were renewed practices since the early 1960s and offered students valuable insight into the experiences of their contemporaries. This suggests that the "Iron Curtain" was more prone to perforation than it seemed to be. Furthermore, the state's initiation of these connections suggests that the officials must have been aware of the different political influences that the chosen students were prone to encounter. However, it must be noted that the archival material did not mention any conditions under which the students from Czechoslovakia were allowed to travel abroad suggesting that only the students with early-Party affiliation were permitted to do so, since even the British Council anticipated that Czechoslovak university students either came from families with good Party record or were active in Party politics.¹⁴⁰ Nonetheless, transnational structures are evident from the discussion, thus, it can be argued that transnational elements of Czechoslovak student activism had developed during the 1960s and only reached their peak in 1968.

¹⁴⁰ TNA, BW 27/22, "University Interchange Scheme (1958–1968)," H. Harvey Wood's Telegram, October 28, 1958.

Transnational Dynamic of the Prague Spring

The Prague Spring

The term “Prague Spring” describes a period of implementation of liberal policies in politics, culture and economics unparalleled in Czechoslovakia before 1968.¹⁴¹ Although named “spring” the process of change can be most radically observed since January 1968, when Alexander Dubček replaced Antonín Novotný as the General Secretary of the KSČ. Additionally, Ludvík Svoboda succeeded Novotný as Czechoslovak president on 30 March 1968. These changes on the highest political level marked the beginning of the subsequent liberalisation. Reforms, which the so-called Action Programme of the KSČ from April 1968 articulated, “increased freedom of speech and the press, and introduced economic reforms to improve the quality and availability of consumer goods,” but still stressed the leading role of KSČ.¹⁴² Unsurprisingly, these policy changes caught the watchful eye of the Soviet Union, but also of the Western bloc. Students had their own perspectives on these reforms.

The Perspective of Czechoslovak and British Students

An important part of the development of the student movement in Czechoslovakia was the foundation of a new student union, namely the Union of University Students of Bohemia and Moravia (*Svaz vysokoškolského studenstva Čech a Moravy*, SVS). The SVS was established in late May 1968 in Olomouc, and it theoretically replaced the communist-overseen ČSM.¹⁴³ Additionally, student magazines, some of them in print since the mid-1960s, reveal information about student engagement in the social and political reformation of 1968. A journal called *Student*, for example, contained SVS’s appeal to the Czechoslovak government for improvement of democracy in the lives of the general public, but also demanded betterment of student experience, such as “allowing internships and stays abroad, regardless of the political system of the country visited.”¹⁴⁴ Thus, students acknowledged their part in wider society; however, they also saw an opportunity in the Prague Spring to benefit their own social group. In addition, as Galia Golan correctly suggests, students in 1968 served as a coercive and efficient body in society.¹⁴⁵

¹⁴¹ James R. Arnold, and Roberta Wiener, *Cold War: The Essential Reference Guide* (Santa Barbara: ABC-CLIO, 2012), 179.

¹⁴² Cashman, “Remembering 1948 and 1968,” 1648.

¹⁴³ Milan Otáhal, *Studenti a komunistická moc v českých zemích 1968–1989* (Prague: Dokořán, 2003), 19.

¹⁴⁴ “Voko Bere,” *Student* 4, no. 30 (24 June 1968), 2, accessed via Československé dokumentační středisko (hereafter: ČSDS), February 22, 2022, <http://www.cds.cz/cs/g6/5598-DS.html>.

¹⁴⁵ Galia Golan, “Youth and Politics in Czechoslovakia,” *Journal of Contemporary History* 5, no. 1 (1970): 15, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/259977>.

Nonetheless, the student experience of the Prague Spring had also its transnational dimension. Indeed, Czechoslovaks were experiencing unprecedented freedom of speech but also freedom of movement. The estimates state that “690.622 citizens travelled to the West” between 1968 and the spring of 1969.¹⁴⁶ However, the travel stream went also the other way around as Paul Hofmann noted in a 1968 article for the *New York Times*: “Young Czechoslovaks and young foreigners drink beer together in taverns, they go together to the movies and discuss them afterwards, they hold joint dances and folk song sessions.”¹⁴⁷ Nevertheless, not all the youth shared the same opinions. According to a British visitor, Nick Wright, who played a significant role in the Hornsey College of Art protest, Czechoslovak youth appeared to be idealising the West and when he returned from his travels, he “was firmly of the view that the Red Army needed to intervene.”¹⁴⁸

On the other side of the spectrum, Czechoslovak students often disagreed with their Western peers over the question of socialism, which many young activists in the West idealised.¹⁴⁹ Nonetheless, despite disputes, caused mainly by different life experiences, some activists held high promises of utilising these transnational connections. Richard Ivan Jobs reports the hopes of one activist who hoped that travel could enable Prague youth to access new experiences, ideas and interactions in the West and to incorporate itself into the Western “transnational movement for social change.”¹⁵⁰ Furthermore, the transnational interactions can also be demonstrated through the televised BBC debate panel for “Students in Revolt” which saw students from Belgium, Britain, Czechoslovakia, Italy, Japan, Spain, the United States, and Yugoslavia participating in a discussion about the student movement in a world-wide perspective.¹⁵¹ Interestingly, the Czechoslovak representative, Jan Kavan, who later emigrated to the United Kingdom and consequently benefited from the structures, observed a “gap between [student activists’] perceptions and aims” during the BBC programme, illustrating that the goals of each student leader in the debate differed based on the various “social systems.”¹⁵² Nevertheless, it is possible to argue that the Prague Spring

¹⁴⁶ James Mark, Anna von der Goltz, “Encounters,” in *Europe’s 1968*, eds. Gildea, Mark, and Warring, 134.

¹⁴⁷ Paul Hofmann, “For Those Under 30, Prague Seems the Right Place to Be This Summer,” *New York Times*, August 12, 1968, 13, <https://www.proquest.com/news/docview/118259636/abstract/C62E70946AC942C7PO/1>. Hofmann reports that the language barrier was not an issue since some degree of German, French and English was common in Prague.

¹⁴⁸ Mark and von der Goltz, “Encounters,” in *Europe’s 1968*, eds. Gildea, Mark, and Warring, 147. The Hornsey College of Art protest took the form of a sit-in on May 28, 1968. The students’ demands included the reform of higher education. Although this protest was eventually defeated, it inspired demonstrations at other art colleges. See Hoefflerle, *British Student Activism in the Long Sixties*, pp. 124–126.

¹⁴⁹ Paulina Bren, “1968 East and West: Visions of Political Change and Student Protest from across the Iron Curtain,” in *Transnational Moments of Change*, eds. Rainer Horn and Padraic Kenney (Lanham: Rowman & Littlefield, 2004), 132.

¹⁵⁰ Jobs, *Backpack Ambassadors*, 129.

¹⁵¹ Jobs, “Youth Movements,” 388. The roundtable was almost cancelled due to the fact that BBC acted without the government’s approval in inviting the student radicals to the UK.

¹⁵² Moreover, after the Velvet Revolution in 1989, Kavan became Czech Minister of Foreign Affairs (1998–2002) and represented the Czech Republic during its admission to NATO on 12 March 1999. Jan Kavan, “Czechoslovakia 1968: Revolt or Reform? 1968 - A Year of Hope and Non-Understanding,” *Critique* 36, no. 2 (2008): 295, doi:10.1080/03017600802185415.

facilitated the increase in the development of social contacts between students of different nationalities with diverse opinions on political reforms.

Warsaw Pact Invasion and its Effect on Students

Although the reforms put in place during the Prague Spring seemed promising for the public, the atmosphere of liberalisation did not last long. The reform process in Czechoslovakia was marked as an “internal counter-revolution” by the Soviet Union and used as an excuse for an invasion by armies of the Warsaw Pact on the night of 20–21 August 1968.¹⁵³

Some students were located outside of Czechoslovakia at the time of the invasion. Due to the unprecedented travel increase to and from Czechoslovakia, as described above, many students found themselves in the situation of emigrating or being stranded in foreign countries, such as the United Kingdom. It is estimated that around 2.600 Czechoslovak students were in Britain in August 1968.¹⁵⁴ The United Kingdom officially condemned the invasion and accepted numerous refugees, according to Milada Polišenská.¹⁵⁵ Almost a year after the invasion, newspapers reported that Britain, among Austria and Sweden, “took about 2.000 refugees.”¹⁵⁶ The demonstration in support of Czechoslovakia, which erupted in front of the Soviet Embassy in London on 21 August, included for example Tariq Ali, a significant figure in the British student movement at the time, who took part in the above-mentioned BBC panel “Students in Revolt” alongside the Czechoslovak citizen Jan Kavan.¹⁵⁷ Moreover, already on 23 August, newspapers informed about a “liaison committee to establish scholarships at the British universities for Czechoslovak students” and the information desk set up by the NUS.¹⁵⁸ Young Czechoslovaks immediately used the NUS helpdesk as they wanted “to know whether they would be allowed to take places in British universities,” similarly to Hungarian student escapees in 1956.¹⁵⁹ Furthermore, the NUS played

¹⁵³ Cashman, “Remembering 1948 and 1968,” 1648-49.

¹⁵⁴ Modern Records Centre, Warwick University (hereafter: MRC), “MSS.280/29/1, Czechoslovak Student Fund,” Memorandum on Czechoslovak Students in Great Britain, 4 November 1968.

¹⁵⁵ Milada Polišenská, “Postoj britského Foreign Office k československému exilovému hnutí,” in *Studie z dějin emigrace*, eds. Jana Burešová and Jana Pelikánová. (Olomouc: Univerzita Palackého v Olomouci, 2010), 10.

¹⁵⁶ Adolf Hermann, “Regretted in Prague but Welcomed Elsewhere”, *Financial Times*, June 11, 1969, <https://link.gale.com/apps/doc/HS2304805045/GDCS?sid=bookmark-GDCS&id=9cef2307>.

¹⁵⁷ “Arrests in London Protest,” *The Times*, 22 August 1968,

<https://link.gale.com/apps/doc/CS17788694/TTDA?sid=bookmark-TTDA&id=0040b769>. Ali recalls that ‘five thousand demonstrators responded’ to the call for protest at the embassy. See Tariq Ali, *Street Fighting Years: An Autobiography of the Sixties* (London: Verso, 2005), 286.

¹⁵⁸ Dennis Barker, “Scholarship Scheme Afoot for Stranded Czechs,” *The Guardian*, August 23, 1968, <https://www.proquest.com/hnp-guardianobserver/docview/185281213/citation/65CE396BF4704D1FPO/14>.

¹⁵⁹ Pat Healy, “Students Want to Stay in Britain to Continue Courses,” *The Times*, August 24, 1968, <https://link.gale.com/apps/doc/CS134573848/TTDA?sid=bookmark-TTDA&id=313d1bf2>.

also a crucial role in informing British authorities about students who wished to remain in the United Kingdom.¹⁶⁰

Additionally, the NUS alongside the Scottish Union of Students, the Welsh Union of Students, the British Youth Council, and the United Nations Student Association were at the birth of the *Czechoslovak Student's Scholarship Fund* (CSSF) which helped stranded students to complete their studies in the United Kingdom. Lord Murray of Newhaven launched the CSSF on 23 October 1968, and in its first year, it assisted almost 300 students while collecting over £100,000.¹⁶¹ Christopher Seton-Watson became The Chairman of the CSSF and World University Service administered the Fund.¹⁶² Interestingly, as Michael G. Thickett mentions in one of his letters on behalf of Ivan Hartel, a Czechoslovak student activist who “played a significant role in the student movement to democratic Czechoslovakia,” the NUS became involved in the CSSF “primarily because of people with records like his.”¹⁶³ Arguably, the fact that Czechoslovak student activists aimed their agenda on democratisation played a vital role in NUS’s decision. Additionally, the case of the already-mentioned Jan Kavan illustrates that those transnational structures became extremely beneficial after the August crisis. As mentioned above, Kavan took part in the BBC panel “Students in Revolt,” establishing networks that might have played a role while applying for grants from CSSF.¹⁶⁴ Moreover, not only the NUS was involved in helping Czechoslovak students abroad, but also kept in touch with the Czechoslovak SVS until its dissolution in the summer of 1969, as demonstrated by correspondence between presidents of the respective unions.¹⁶⁵ This shows that although the Czechoslovak and British student unions were not part of the same international bodies (ISC, IUS), they maintained transnational contacts, further illustrating the permissiveness of national boundaries and the “Iron Curtain.” The CSSF closed its application

¹⁶⁰ TNA, BW 27/31, “USSR Occupation of Czechoslovakia: Effect on British Council Activities,” September 12, 1968.

¹⁶¹ MRC, MSS.280/29/1, “Czechoslovak Student Fund,” Czechoslovak Students Who Choose Freedom in Britain, January 24, 1969. To compare, in the first year of the Soviet invasion of Hungary, British universities accepted around 150 Hungarian students and advertised the *Hungarian Student's Scholarship Fund*. See From Our Special Correspondent, “Students From Hungary,” *The Times*, January 2, 1957, <https://link.gale.com/apps/doc/CS152786978/GDCS?sid=bookmark-GDCS&xid=d6b71e0a>; Ann Kneif, “After the Uprising of 1956: Hungarian Students in Britain,” *The Historian* 92 (Winter 2006): 26; Lindsay D. Keir, John F. Lockwood, and Stephen Spender., “Hungary,” *The Times*, November 16, 1956, <https://link.gale.com/apps/doc/CS185816944/GDCS?sid=bookmark-GDCS&xid=7a90c0d3>.

¹⁶² MRC, MSS.280/29/1, “Czechoslovak Student Fund,” Letter dated 21 January 1969. Christopher Seton-Watson (1918–2007) was a historian of Italy, the son of a historian of Eastern and Southern Europe, Robert William Seton-Watson (1879–1951), who co-established the School of Slavonic and East European Studies at the University College London in 1915. See, for example, R. B. Betts, “Robert William Seton-Watson, 1879–1951,” *The Slavonic and East European Review* 30, no. 74 (1951): 252–55, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/4204301>; John Pollard, “Christopher Seton-Watson,” *The Guardian*, December 4, 2007, <https://www.theguardian.com/news/2007/dec/04/guardianobituaries.internationaleducationnews>.

¹⁶³ MRC, MSS.280/29/1, “Czechoslovak Student Fund,” letter dated December 16, 1968.

¹⁶⁴ MRC, MSS.280/29/1, “Czechoslovak Student Fund,” letter from Michael Thickett, July 1969. It must be noted here that Jan Kavan has not yet responded to the author’s efforts to interview him on benefiting from the CSSF.

¹⁶⁵ MRC, MSS.280/29/1, “Czechoslovak Student Fund,” letter dated June 14, 1969.

process towards the end of 1970.¹⁶⁶ Barbara Day suggested that “after the flood of generosity (...) for students trapped in Britain (...) sponsorship for Czechoslovak efforts became scarce.”¹⁶⁷ Nevertheless, archival materials suggest otherwise, as the CSSF continued providing grants during three academic years (1968–1971), it distributed over £143.000 to 639 students in need.¹⁶⁸

Regarding student exchanges, the British Foreign Office did not plan to abandon agreements under the Anglo-Czechoslovak Programme due to the lack of “any obvious sign of Soviet supervision or interference.”¹⁶⁹ Nonetheless, slightly later, signs of doubt about the continuance of the scheme started to spring to the surface on the Czechoslovak side.¹⁷⁰ Surprisingly for the Foreign Office, the Czechoslovak Ministry of Foreign Affairs banned “all students and journalists” from entering the country on 30 September 1968.¹⁷¹ This also included students under the cultural agreement. However, subsequent negotiations indicate the resumption of exchanges in the following years.¹⁷² Although the exchanges were temporarily postponed, the Warsaw Pact occupation did not lead to any withdrawal from agreements between the two countries.

This part of the article discussed the transnational student networks of the Czechoslovak student movement to demonstrate their usefulness in times of crisis. The NUS records have illustrated that activism enabled students in both countries to make transnational structures. These ties then led to significant help from British students to their Czechoslovak peers who emigrated or were stranded in the UK due to the occupation. *Czechoslovak Student's Scholarship Fund* helped students to study and consequently build a life in the United Kingdom. Therefore, it can be concluded that transnational connections enabled some student activists to overcome the unfortunate political situation.¹⁷³

¹⁶⁶ MRC, MSS.280/29/1, “Czechoslovak Student Fund,” *Czechoslovak Student's Scholarship Fund*, Second Annual Report, 1969–1970.

¹⁶⁷ Barbara Day, “The Democratic Exile Movement from the Soviet Bloc Countries in GB: An English Perspective,” in *Studie z dějin emigrace*, eds. Jana Burešová and Jitka Pelikánová (Olomouc: Univerzita Palackého v Olomouci, 2010), 28.

¹⁶⁸ MRC, MSS.280/29/1, “Czechoslovak Student Fund,” Third Annual Report, 1970–71.

¹⁶⁹ TNA, BW 27/31, “USSR Occupation of Czechoslovakia: Effect on British Council Activities,” letters from September 4–6, 1968.

¹⁷⁰ TNA, BW 27/31, “USSR Occupation of Czechoslovakia: Effect on British Council Activities,” F. D. Hughes' letter, September 19, 1968.

¹⁷¹ TNA, BW 27/31, “USSR Occupation of Czechoslovakia: Effect on British Council Activities,” telegram no. 476, September 30, 1968.

¹⁷² TNA, BW 27/31, “UK-Czechoslovakia Programme of Cultural Exchanges 1970–1972: Negotiations, Brief,” December 1, 1968 – December 31, 1971.

¹⁷³ However, it needs to be mentioned that the Soviet invasion of Czechoslovakia did not cause the termination of cultural agreements between Czechoslovakia and the United Kingdom, as the talks about university exchanges continued for the year 1969. See TNA, *Ibid.*

Conclusion

The discussed period of student activism remains a fascinating phenomenon for research not only from a national perspective but also from a transnational one. The interactions between Czechoslovak and British students began well before the Second World War. After the communist coup in 1948, and the consequent shift of Czechoslovakia behind the “Iron Curtain,” these structures were disrupted with the sole exception of Czechoslovak students opposing the February coup, travelling to the NUS conference in the United Kingdom to plead for help.

Student exchanges within the agenda of scholarships and summer camps function as another expression of transnational structures in the Czechoslovak student movement. The Programme of British and Czechoslovak Cultural Exchange resumed in the early 1960s, providing students from both countries with opportunities for interaction and for experiencing their contemporaries’ lives. It has, therefore, been demonstrated that the “Iron Curtain” was permeable. Furthermore, transnational ties between the two student bodies had gained momentum long before 1968 when they achieved their height.

Finally, the focus on the Prague Spring reform process is tied to the response of British students to the August invasion. The structures, established through the years preceding the occupation, were crucial in the decision of British students to help their Czechoslovak counterparts in times of crisis, thus illustrating transnational dimensions. As some students emigrated or were stranded in the United Kingdom, their British peers aided them through solidarity campaigns and the *Czechoslovak Students’ Scholarship Fund*, which over three years of its existence distributed around £143.000 to over six hundred Czechoslovak students in need. Furthermore, the archival material suggests that NUS and SVS maintained transnational connections despite operating in rival international student organisations. Thus, once again the permeability of the “Iron Curtain” has been highlighted.

Overall, this paper has demonstrated that despite diverse political persuasions and life experiences, Czechoslovak students were part of a wider, transnationally dynamic, student movement. Therefore, the study of transnational student movements, such as that from Czechoslovakia, can provide further nuance to our understanding of the Cold War.

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